

Effectiveness of Principal-Initiated Programmes in Enhancing the Retention of Teenage Mothers in Public Secondary Schools in Nyali Sub-County Mombasa County

By

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Abstract

The study aimed to examine ways principal-initiated programmes enhance the retention of teenage mothers in public secondary schools in Nyali sub-county Mombasa county. It was guided by one research question: What programs have principals initiated to support the retention of teenage mothers? The study was grounded in Emile Durkheim's Social Integration Theory and employed a mixed-methods research approach using a convergent parallel design. Both descriptive cross-sectional and phenomenological research approaches were integrated. Sampling techniques included stratified random, simple random, systematic random, and purposive sampling. The target population comprised 1,750 Form Three and Four students, principals, SCDE and 265 teachers across seven public secondary schools. The sample included 165 students, 131 teachers, four principals, and one sub-county director of education. Data collection instruments included questionnaires, in-depth interview guides, and focus group discussion guides. Instrument reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha for quantitative tools, and member checking, triangulation, and peer review for qualitative tools. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, while qualitative data were analyzed using thematic methods. Findings revealed that principals have implemented initiatives such as healthcare assistance, counselling, reintegration policies, and flexible timetables to support teenage mothers. The study concluded that while principal-initiated programs are essential for retaining teenage mothers in school, sustained parental involvement and broader community collaboration are vital for achieving long-term success. Recommendations included standardizing retention programs across schools, enhancing parent engagement through workshops, improving teacher preparation, and forming partnerships with local stakeholders.

Key Words: Teenage mothers school retention programs, principal-initiated programs, Reintegration policies, education retention.

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Background to the Problem

Teenage mothers, defined as young women who give birth before the age of 20, are disproportionately affected by challenges such as poverty, orphan-hood, abuse, forced sex, and limited educational opportunities (Janina, 2021). These difficulties are further compounded in disadvantaged regions, where teenage pregnancies often result in severe health and social repercussions. For instance, complications related to pregnancy and childbirth are the leading causes of death for girls aged 15–19 globally, accounting for 99% of maternal fatalities among women aged 15–49 (Janina, 2021). Additionally, teenage mothers and their children face significant obstacles, including limited access to healthcare, education, and financial resources, often exacerbated by social stigma and the lack of support networks (UNICEF, 2023; WHO, 2022). Retention programs aimed at supporting teenage mothers in education are crucial in addressing these challenges. Retention, in this context, refers to strategies that ensure adolescent mothers remain enrolled and engaged in school. Research shows that interventions such as flexible schedules, re-entry policies, and school-based counseling services significantly enhance educational outcomes for teenage mothers (Nguyen et al., 2023). However, the effective implementation of these programs remains a challenge, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa. Cultural stigma, inadequate support structures, and inconsistent policy enforcement hinder the success of retention initiatives, as observed in countries like Kenya, where 18% of girls aged 15–19 have begun childbearing, with higher rates in regions like Nyali Sub-County, Mombasa (KNBS, 2020). Despite government efforts, including the 2020 National Guidelines for School Retention, barriers such as stigma, insufficient stakeholder involvement, and the socioeconomic impacts of COVID-19 continue to limit progress (MoE, 2020; National Council for Population and Development, 2020).

Retention programs aim to ensure teenage mothers remain enrolled and engaged in education by addressing needs such as mental health care, childcare support, and stigma mitigation (Kochhar-Bryant et al., 2023). Effective practices include flexible schedules and academic support, and collaboration among parents, schools, and communities plays a crucial role (Olufunke et al., 2023; Mwangi & Chege, 2022). Despite these efforts, implementation challenges persist, especially in

sub-Saharan Africa, where teenage pregnancy continues to disrupt educational access (UNESCO, 2019; Njoroge & Muhia, 2019). The global community, through SDGs and the MDGs, emphasizes inclusive education for all, highlighting the importance of empowering women and addressing inequalities (Mutua, 2019; Imbosa et al., 2022; UNICEF).

Numerous programs have been put in place in industrialized nations to assist adolescent moms in pursuing higher education. For example, in Australia, young moms can finish high school while taking care of their children thanks to Melbourne's Young Parents Education Program (YPEP). This program helps students manage their academic and family obligations by providing flexible learning environments and on-site daycare (Herald Sun, 2024). In a similar vein, the School-Based Child Care Program in the US gives adolescent moms access to childcare services inside of schools, increasing their retention and graduation rates (National Women's Law Center, 2023).

A number of African nations have enacted laws to facilitate adolescent mothers' return to school. The Strategic Approaches to females' Education (STAGE) initiative in Ghana helps females who are at risk, such as adolescent mothers, to go back to school. This program lowers the risk of subsequent pregnancies by empowering young women to make educated reproductive decisions in addition to emphasizing education (Exemplars Health, 2023). To give adolescent moms in Tanzania equal access to education and assistance, initiatives have been put in place to enroll them in the formal secondary school system (ResearchGate, 2024).

Principals in Kenya have started initiatives to improve the retention of adolescent mothers in public secondary schools, specifically in Nyali Sub-County, Mombasa County. To meet the special needs of young mothers, these programs offer flexible school schedules, guidance and counseling services, and vocational training (Africana Journal Articles, 2024). Furthermore, groups like CFK Africa have started initiatives like the Funzo Project with the goal of enhancing the economic prospects, health, and well-being of adolescent moms in order to encourage their return to education (IDinsight, 2023). Notwithstanding these initiatives, issues like stigma, a lack of funding, and gaps in policy implementation still exist, calling for ongoing support and lobbying to guarantee the academic achievement of adolescent mothers in the area.

Statement of the Problem

Globally, teenage motherhood presents significant challenges, with school dropout rates among teenage mothers being alarmingly high due to factors like inadequate support systems and stigma (UNESCO, 2021). Research across various regions, including sub-Saharan Africa, has shown that teenage mothers face unique educational and social barriers, including discrimination and lack of childcare, which hinder their academic progress (World Bank, 2020; Al-Mutairi, 2021). In Kenya, the issue is compounded by socio-cultural beliefs that stigmatize teenage mothers, contributing to lower retention rates in schools (Nyambegera & Kiplagat, 2019; Imbosa, Majanga, & Ouda, 2022). In Kenya's Nyali Sub-County, despite school principals initiating programs to support teenage mothers, studies indicate that these initiatives are often inadequately implemented, leading to limited effectiveness in addressing dropout rates (Echessa, 2021). The social cry for educational equity and the right to education for all, including teenage mothers, underscores the urgency of this issue (UNICEF, 2022). This study aimed to explore the effectiveness of principals' initiated programs in enhancing teenage mothers' retention in public secondary schools in Nyali sub-county, Mombasa county, Kenya.

Research Question

In what ways do principal-initiated programmes enhance the retention of teenage mothers in public secondary schools in Nyali sub-county?

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in Emile Durkheim's Social Integration Theory, which explores the importance of social cohesion within communities and how integrating individuals, such as teenage mothers, into the school system can foster unity and reduce disparities. According to Durkheim, social integration is essential for forming a collective consciousness that directs social interactions and norms (Sourabh, 2023). His theory suggests that shared beliefs and values contribute to stronger interpersonal connections and a sense of belonging, which is vital for enhancing retention strategies in schools. In the context of public secondary schools in Nyali sub-

county, Mombasa County, effective school leadership practices that promote inclusive environments can help integrate teenage mothers and bridge social gaps without erasing their unique identities (Karima & Boutouchent, 2020).

Durkheim's ideas also emphasize the role of social control, where individuals' adherence to societal norms is driven by personal integrity and moral values rather than external enforcement (Follert, 2019). This internal control fosters compliance and reduces deviant behavior, supporting a stable social structure. In educational settings, creating a culture of inclusion and reminding students of the value of community norms can contribute significantly to retention programs for teenage mothers. By cultivating a sense of belonging and unity, schools can enhance social integration and promote positive attitudes and behaviors among students, ultimately boosting their academic and personal well-being (Picciotto, 2021; IvyPanda, 2023).

Review of Related Empirical Literature

Lourdes, Gomez, MaryJane, and Omandam (2023) conducted a qualitative single case research with the aim of investigating the experiences of secondary school teachers in the Philippines from 2021–2022 to 2022–2023 about their assistance of pregnant students and young moms. Field notes, observations, and in-depth interviews were some of the data gathering techniques used. The study employed categorical analysis to examine how instructors responded to difficulties they faced, teacher-initiated support techniques, academic support, and how young moms responded to the help they received. In addition to stressing the need for counseling skills and resolving absenteeism and late assignment submission, teachers stated feeling conflicted about their feelings and worries for the long-term wellbeing of their pupils. A number of initiatives were suggested, including in-depth discussions, using ICT for outreach, offering monetary and in-kind help, setting up extracurricular activities, giving school supplies, switching to blended learning, and making house calls. Whatever their marital status, instructors' strategies for dealing with adolescent moms and pregnancies differed depending on the circumstances of each student, but when school officials backed them, the results were favorable. When given thorough academic support, teenage moms showed enthusiasm and continued to be interested in their studies. This study emphasized how

crucial principal-initiated programs are for helping teenage mothers stay in secondary schools and succeed academically.

The goal of teenage mothers' retention and re-entry programme is to assist them in gaining access to and be kept in regular secondary schools until they graduate. However, because school discipline is characterized by suspension, the practice is still deficient. re-entry into another school or expulsion. In order to identify intervention measures to improve retention and re-entry, Kawala's (2021) study set out to investigate stakeholders' perceptions of the re-entry programmes and practices for teenage mothers in secondary schools in Malongo, Sub-County, Mayuge District, Uganda. The ecological system theory of Urie Bronfenbrenner served as the study's guiding theory. The study used a phenomenological research methodology with an interpretivist approach, which allowed the researcher to investigate stakeholders' perspectives on the effectiveness of retention and re-entry programmes and practices for teenage mothers. Teenage mothers, head teachers, education authorities, and teachers in charge of female child programmes were among the target group. Data was gathered for teenage mothers through in-depth interviews and drawings. Key informants were chosen using snowball sampling and purposeful sampling procedures. Thematic analysis was used to analyze the data. The survey found that stakeholders' views had somewhat improved and that they were somewhat aware of the programmes effectiveness surrounding secondary school retention and re-entry. This can serve as a solid base for policymakers to improve retention and re-entry programmes and systems. While a divergence in the structures and processes would undermine the attempts to improve retention and re-entry, these are fairly certain solutions to bridge the gap between the policy and practices.

The study by Opondo, and Aloka (2020). investigated the Guidance and Counselling Programme and Adjustment of Teenage Mothers in Secondary Schools in Kenya. The study used a Causal-Comparative ex post facto research design. 242 teenage mothers who had been retained from certain schools in Ugenya Sub County, Kenya, were the study's target group. The sample size consisted of 104 retained teenage mothers who were reintegrated back into the school without participating in the counselling programme, and 138 retained teenage mothers who completed the counselling programme. To gather data, questionnaires were utilized, including the Academic Adjustment Questionnaire, Social Adjustment Questionnaire, Emotional Adjustment

Questionnaire, Psychological Adjustment Questionnaire, and Attitude toward Guidance and Counselling Questionnaire. According to the study's findings, teenage mothers received the greatest ratings for social adjustment and the lowest ratings for academic adjustment. On the other hand, the study's conclusions showed that students who had received formal counselling often recorded more adjustments than those who had not. The association between the guiding and counselling programme and the adjustment of teenage mothers was mediated by the attitude of the teenage mothers. Guidance and counselling services should be offered by school administrators to ensure that teenage mothers adjust to school life holistically.

Research Design and Methodology

The study on principal-initiated programs aimed at enhancing the retention of teenage mothers in public secondary schools in Nyali Sub-County employed a convergent parallel mixed-method design, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches. This design facilitated the simultaneous collection and analysis of data from both methods, providing an understanding of the research topic (Malau-Aduli & Alele, 2023).

The quantitative component utilized a cross-sectional survey to examine specific principal-initiated programs designed to support the retention of teenage mothers. This approach enabled the collection of detailed and structured data on these programs. Meanwhile, the qualitative aspect employed a phenomenological approach to explore experiences of students and educators. By focusing on lived experiences within the educational setting, the study provided insights into the effectiveness of these programs. Neubauer, Witkop, and Varpio (2019) highlight that phenomenological approaches are valuable for understanding complex human experiences, such as retention of teenage mothers. The mixed-method design offered a holistic perspective on the effectiveness of principal-initiated programs in retaining teenage mothers in Nyali Sub-County.

Locale of the Study

Nyali Sub-County has seven public secondary schools and twelve private ones. Nyali is a residential area and sub-county within Mombasa City, located on the mainland north of Mombasa County. It is connected to Mombasa Island by the New Nyali Bridge. All seven public secondary

schools in the sub-county are day schools (Mombasa County Government, 2022). Nyali Sub-County is well known for its coastal location, characterized by a mix of commercial and residential areas. The socioeconomic conditions in the sub-county are notably uneven, with both affluent and underprivileged areas. Students' academic performance in Nyali Sub-County is significantly affected by high rates of teenage pregnancy, which stem from disparities in communities' access to educational institutions.

Target Population

The target population, as defined by Creswell (2023), refers to the entire group of individuals or units from whom data is collected to make inferences. In this study, the target population comprised 2,023 respondents, including 7 principals, 165 teachers, one sub-county director of education, and 1,750 students.

Description of the Sampling Procedures and Sample Size

In line with Kothari's (2019) recommendations, the researcher employed both probability and non-probability sampling techniques to ensure a representative sample for data collection in the study on principal-initiated programs aimed at enhancing the retention of teenage mothers. Given the mixed-method approach, a combination of stratified, purposive, simple random, and systematic sampling methods was used. Stephanie (2022) suggests that a sample size of 10% of the population is typically sufficient, provided it does not exceed 1,000 participants. Following this guideline, the researcher selected 4 out of 7 public day secondary schools in Nyali Sub-County using stratified sampling to ensure representation across various school categories. From these schools, 7 principals were included through purposive sampling due to their leadership roles and valuable insights into retention programs for teenage mothers. Additionally, 131 out of 165 teachers were chosen using simple random sampling to provide equal participation opportunities. Finally, systematic sampling was applied to select 175 out of 1,175 students, ensuring balanced representation within the student population.

Description of Research Instruments

A research instrument is a tool designed to systematically collect data to quantify observable social and natural phenomena (Sugiyono, as cited in Sugiharto, 2018). These instruments are primarily employed to gather data that addresses specific research questions. In the study on principal-initiated programs aimed at enhancing the retention of teenage mothers, both quantitative and qualitative research tools were used to ensure a comprehensive approach to data collection. Structured questionnaires were utilized to gather quantitative data, enabling standardized responses suitable for statistical analysis. For qualitative insights, focus group discussion guides and in-depth interview guides were employed to explore participants' perspectives and experiences more deeply. To further enrich the data and enhance understanding of the research topic, supplementary methods such as document analysis and observation checklists were also incorporated (Sugiyono, as cited in Sugiharto, 2018).

Validity of Research Instruments

The validity of a research instrument is crucial, as it ensures that the tool accurately and reliably measures the intended variables (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). In the study investigating the effectiveness of principal-initiated programs on enhancing the retention of teenage mothers, maintaining consistency in research instruments was essential to address potential uncertainties and deficiencies, thereby improving the tool's effectiveness (DeVellis, 2019). To ensure content validity, experts reviewed the instruments to confirm their relevance to the research topic. Based on their feedback, the instruments were refined and adjusted to enhance their accuracy and alignment with the study's objectives.

Reliability of Research Instruments

The reliability of a research instrument refers to its ability to consistently produce stable results across repeated applications (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2018). In the study examining the effectiveness of principal-initiated programs in enhancing the retention of teenage mothers, reliability was ensured by pre-testing the instruments on a subset of students from the intended participant pool. The internal consistency of the instruments was evaluated using Cronbach's

Alpha, a statistical measure where higher values indicate greater reliability. Cronbach's Alpha ranges from 0 to 1, with a higher coefficient reflecting a strong correlation among items, thereby confirming the consistency of the instrument in measuring the research topic (Middleton, 2023). In this study, a Cronbach's Alpha value between 0.6 and 0.7 was considered acceptable, while a value of 0.8 or higher indicated excellent reliability.

Pilot Testing of the Research Instruments

A small, representative sample of the study population is typically used for pilot testing, an initial trial of the research instruments. This process helps identify any issues with the instruments and allows for necessary adjustments. In this study, the researcher administered the instrument to a small group of participants representative of the target population. Participants were asked to rate the items based on difficulty, relevance, and clarity. The researcher used their feedback to refine the tool, including rewording unclear items, removing unnecessary questions, and adding relevant ones, as recommended by Mugenda and Mugenda (2018). For the current study, a pilot test was conducted with respondents from two schools, including both students and teachers. The pilot study assessed the accuracy, clarity, and suitability of the instruments to ensure their validity and reliability.

Description of Data Collection Procedures

The Department of Postgraduate Studies in Education at the Catholic University of Eastern Africa provided the researcher with a letter of introduction. Subsequently, the researcher applied for and obtained a permit to collect data from the National Council for Science, Technology, and Innovation (NACOSTI). Additionally, authorization was secured from the Nyali Education Office to conduct research within the sub-county. The researcher scheduled appointments with school principals to conduct research at prearranged dates and times, ensuring minimal disruption to the schools and reducing unannounced visits without prior notice or explanation. The researcher personally distributed questionnaires to each teacher at the sampled schools, allowing them sufficient time to complete them. Once completed, the questionnaires were collected. In preparation for interviews, the researcher arranged in-person meetings with the sub-county director of education and the principals. During these interviews, the researcher took detailed notes and

recorded the data as necessary. Focus group discussions with students were conducted by the researcher, supported by two assistants, to gather additional qualitative insights.

Description of Data Analysis Procedures

Following the data collection process, the completed questionnaires were indexed and entered into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) application for easy access and analysis. Backup copies of both the input and output data were created and securely stored to prevent data loss. The analysis employed both qualitative and quantitative methods, enabling the researcher to overcome the limitations of using a single approach and obtain a more comprehensive dataset (Creswell, 2017). For the quantitative data, descriptive statistics such as percentages, frequency tables, and pie charts were used. Frequency distribution tables and visual figures were employed to present the data, making it easier for readers to interpret trends by examining the tables and charts. The qualitative data from focus group discussions (FGDs) and in-depth interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis. This involved organizing the data, conducting preliminary coding, minimizing redundancy, merging related codes into themes, and reporting the findings in a narrative format in the final report.

Ethical Considerations

Before beginning the research, the researcher obtained the necessary field research approvals from the National Council for Science and Technology (NACOSTI) through the Department of Postgraduate Studies at the Catholic University of Eastern Africa. Following this, the researcher secured a formal authorization letter from the Sub-County Director of Education for Nyali Sub-County to visit the four selected schools. To facilitate access to Form Three students and related documents for analysis, the researcher visited the schools and requested permission to meet with the principals, Form Three and Form Four students, and teachers. The researcher then scheduled the distribution of questionnaires, in-depth interviews, and focus group discussions at times convenient for both the institutions and participants. Adult respondents voluntarily signed consent forms, while student participants provided consent after being informed that their participation was voluntary and that their responses would remain anonymous and confidential. To maintain anonymity, respondents were instructed not to include their names on the questionnaires. Integrity was maintained throughout the entire research process. With the main objective of enhancing

students’ academic performance, the final report was written with honesty and authenticity. Proper citations to other academic works were included to avoid plagiarism.

Findings and Discussions

Respondents were asked to rate how much they agree or disagree with a series of statements on a Likert scale from 5 (strongly agree) to 1 (strongly disagree) in order to assess the efficacy of these efforts. This method will assist in evaluating the ways in which principal-led interventions support teenage mothers' academic achievement and retention in Nyali Sub-County. The results are as shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Ways Principals Initiatives Enhance Retention and Performance of teenage mothers in secondary schools in Nyali according to teachers in the study

No.	Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std Dev
i	Mentorship programmes have a favorable effect on keeping teenage mothers in their roles.	32 33%	38 39%	10 10%	8 8%	10 10%	3.76	1.24
ii	Having daycare centers has a beneficial effect on keeping teenage mothers in the workforce.	26 27%	35 36%	14 14%	10 10%	1 13%	3.53	1.28
iii	Teenage mothers' retention is positively impacted by flexible class scheduling.	20 21%	44 45%	15 15%	8 8%	11 11%	3.56	1.18
iv	Teenage mothers' academic performance is positively impacted by guidance and counseling programmes.	34 35%	40 41%	8 8%	8 8%	8 8%	3.86	1.13
v	Community collaborations have a favorable effect on teenage mothers' retention rates.	25 26%	38 39%	20 20%	6 6%	9 9%	3.66	1.12
vi	Programmes for financial support have a favorable effect on keeping teenage mothers in their homes.	28 29%	35 36%	15 15%	7 7%	13 13%	3.60	1.28
vii	Teenage mothers' retention is positively impacted by peer support groups.	22 23%	36 37%	18 18%	12 12%	10 10%	3.50	1.23
viii	Awareness initiatives have a favorable effect on teenage mothers' academic performance.	24 25%	44 45%	15 15%	8 8%	9 9%	3.66	1.15
ix	Mentorship programmes have a favorable effect on keeping teenage mothers in their roles.	26 26%	40 41%	10 10%	8 8%	14 14%	3.58	1.26

Source: *Field Data (2024)*

The majority of respondents held mentoring programs (Statements I and ix) in high esteem, with a combined 72% (33% strongly agreed and 39% agreed) stating that these activities had a beneficial influence on keeping teenage mothers in school. The mean score of 3.76 indicates a high degree of agreement and significant support for mentoring as a retention strategy. While the majority of respondents were positive, 10% were unsure, and another 18% (8% disagreed and 10% strongly disagreed) were not persuaded of the program's efficacy, according to the standard deviation of 1.24, which shows some variety in viewpoints. This discrepancy shows that more research is required to determine why some respondents are still dubious about the whole advantages of mentorship programs.

Daycare facilities (Statement ii) were likewise favorably perceived by 63% of respondents (of whom 27% strongly agreed and 36% agreed) as a retention tactic for teenage mothers. There was, nevertheless, a noticeable degree of ambiguity and disagreement; 14% expressed confusion, while 23% (10% disagreed and 13% strongly disagreed) expressed mixed perspectives. While the standard deviation of 1.28 indicates a larger range of replies, the mean score of 3.53 indicates considerable agreement. This suggests that respondents' perceptions of the usefulness of childcare centers varied. These results could indicate variations in the way these facilities are used or administered, and more research might assist uncover strategies to raise the initiative's perceived worth.

Strong support was shown for flexible class schedule (Statement iii), with 66% of respondents (21 percent strongly agreed and 45 percent agreed) confirming its beneficial effects on the retention of teenage mothers. While the comparatively low standard deviation of 1.18 reflects a more consistent collection of responses compared to other initiatives, the initiative's mean score of 3.56 suggests widespread acceptance. Flexible scheduling is widely seen as a beneficial approach; but, some respondents may require further knowledge or experience with such programs to fully comprehend their benefits. Only 8% of respondents disagreed, and 15% were unsure. These results imply that a dependable tactic for retaining teenage mothers in school is flexible scheduling.

Programs for guidance and counselling (Statement iv) were the most highly rated, as indicated by the 76% of respondents who agreed (35 percent strongly agreed and 41 percent agreed) that these initiatives had a beneficial effect on teenage mothers' academic achievement. This significant

endorsement is reflected in the initiative's mean score of 3.86, the highest of all. Furthermore, the low standard deviation of 1.13 indicates little variation in the replies, pointing to a high degree of agreement among the participants. The fact that just 16% of respondents (8% disagreed and 8% strongly disagreed) expressed opposition and 8% were unsure highlights how successful guidance and counselling are generally thought to be. This program seems to have the biggest influence on helping teenage mothers succeed academically.

A significant number of respondents (65%) strongly agreed and 39% agreed that community partnerships (Statement v) are advantageous. This suggests that integrating external stakeholders can be beneficial in supporting teenage mothers. The mean score was 3.66, with a noteworthy 20% of respondents expressing uncertainty and 15% expressing misgivings (6% disagreed and 9% strongly disagreed). The 1.12 standard deviation indicates that although the majority of respondents are in favor of community collaboration, a sizeable minority are not sure or disagree with its significance. These results can point to the need for improved community partnership implementation tactics or more efficient communication about how to use them to keep adolescent moms in school.

Programs for financial help (Statement vi) were supported by 65% of respondents (29% strongly agreed and 36% agreed), showing that most people are aware of the beneficial effects of these initiatives on the retention of young mothers. But 15% were unsure, and 20% disagreed (7% strongly disagreed and 13% disagreed), which added up to a mean score of 3.60. In comparison to other projects, attitudes on financial support programs appear to vary more significantly, as indicated by the comparatively high standard deviation of 1.28. This discrepancy may be the result of variations in how financial help is seen or administered in various educational settings, underscoring the necessity of reliable and easily available financial aid programs to adequately assist teenage mothers.

Statement vii on peer support groups received 60% agreement, with 23% strongly agreeing and 37% agreeing, indicating moderate support for the project. However, there seems to be considerable variation in the perception of peer support, with 18% of respondents indicating indecision and 22% (12% disagreeing and 10% strongly disagreeing) expressing dissent. Peer support groups are seen as beneficial by many respondents; however, a sizeable minority are either

unsure or disagree regarding their efficacy, according to the mean score of 3.50 and standard deviation of 1.23. This variation may result from variations in the caliber or design of peer assistance initiatives across various educational institutions.

Initiatives to raise awareness (Statement viii) were highly praised; according to 70% of respondents (25 percent strongly agreed and 45% agreed), they had a good impact on the academic achievement of teenage mothers. The initiative had a mean score of 3.66 and a standard deviation of 1.15, indicating a widespread consensus. However, 17% of respondents (8% disagreed and 9% strongly disagreed) expressed disagreement. These findings imply that although awareness campaigns are typically successful, their execution or scope may yet be enhanced. Raising awareness of the unique difficulties faced by teenage mothers may contribute to improving these students' academic performance, particularly in schools where there are fewer established programs of this kind.

Principals in Nyalı Sub-County revealed in the interviews that they use a number of important metrics to assess the success of programs designed to keep teenage mothers in their roles. According to one of the principals:

Monitoring the retention rates of adolescent moms over time is a significant method. Clear indicator of success is a decline in dropout rates and an increase in the proportion of teenage mothers who finish their school. By keeping an eye on advances in these students' performance, attendance, and involvement in school activities, also gauging their academic growth. In order to make sure the programs are fulfilling the requirements of the teenage mothers, as administrators also we follow up with them on a regular basis. In order to do this, we consult with teachers and counselors to get their opinions on the difficulties they encounter and the assistance they get (NSCPSSP 2 Personal Communication 12 September, 2024).

Additionally, principals have noted that psychological health and emotional toughness of students are key indicators of efficacy. They assess this by looking at the teenage mothers' participation in support groups and therapy, as well as their overall disposition toward education. Principals have observed that the active participation of students in mentoring programs and their sense of belonging within the school community are indicators that the initiatives are having a beneficial influence on their personal and academic progress. Additionally, a few principals emphasized the

value of gathering input from the families and teenage mothers themselves in order to assess the programs' efficacy and pinpoint areas in need of development.

Students, especially teenage mothers, stated in the focus group discussions that they had been successfully encouraged to finish their secondary school by a number of efforts. One of the group discussions observed that:

The value of flexible school schedules, which enable us to balance our academic obligations with their roles as teenage mothers. Our ability to attend school and yet take care of our children was facilitated by the availability of part-time or modified schedules. Furthermore, it is believed that offering childcare or permitting us to send our kids to school when needed, is an essential support system. This made it easier for us to continue attending school by reducing the stress of seeking outside daycare (NSCPSSSP5 Personal Communication 13 September, 2024).

The school's counselling and emotional support services were highly valued by the students, who saw them as essential for managing the pressures of juggling motherhood and schooling. The school-based peer support groups were particularly recognized for helping teenage mothers feel like they belong and for providing a safe space for them to talk about their struggles. These organizations gave students direction and encouragement to remain focused on their study, as did mentoring programs that matched them with female professors or outside mentors. The students believed that these programs encouraged them to finish their secondary school by boosting their self-esteem and resilience in addition to helping them academically. The conclusion that guidance and counselling services are essential in motivating teenage mothers to pursue their secondary education is supported by the findings of Opondo and Aloka's (2020) study. According to their research, teenage mothers who took part in formal counselling programs were able to adjust more socially, emotionally, and psychologically than those who did not. This is consistent with the viewpoints of Nyali Sub-County students, who stressed the value of emotional support and counselling in assisting them in overcoming the difficulties of juggling parenthood and education. The study goes on to say that in order to improve holistic adjustment and increase retention rates among teenage mothers, guidance and counselling services should be included by school administration.

Initiatives designed to encourage teenage mothers to finish their secondary education can benefit from the integration of Transformational Leadership Theory, which highlights the role that school leaders have in inspiring and motivating staff and students alike. Transformational leaders create a welcoming and encouraging school climate that acknowledges the special difficulties experienced by teenage mothers and supports the introduction of specialized programs like flexible scheduling, mentorship, and counselling. Through the dissemination of a common goal and the active involvement of educators and therapists in these endeavors, transformational leaders may foster a climate of understanding and cooperation. By attending to their unique needs, this method not only empowers teenage mothers but also improves their academic experience, which in turn improves retention rates and educational outcomes.

Summary of Findings

According to the study, principal-initiated initiatives including flexible class schedules, school-based childcare centers, and counseling services greatly aid in keeping adolescent moms enrolled in public secondary schools. Additionally, principals work with neighborhood organizations to offer mentorship programs and financial assistance. Full program implementation is hampered by issues including staff capability, money, and social stigma, which suggests that comprehensive policies are required to support these efforts.

Conclusion

Programs started by the principal are essential for removing obstacles that adolescent moms have when trying to finish their education. By delivering targeted solutions like childcare assistance, academic adaptations, and psychological support, these programs enhance inclusivity and academic continuity. The results highlight the value of proactive leadership in establishing supportive learning environments, but systemic issues necessitate cooperation from all parties involved to guarantee long-term results.

Recommendations

The study suggests expanding government funding for school-based initiatives that assist adolescent moms and incorporating these initiatives into more comprehensive national education strategies in order to improve retention. In addition to strengthening relationships with private

organizations and NGOs to supply more resources, principals should be trained in inclusive leadership. Campaigns to raise awareness in the community are crucial to lowering stigma and increasing support for the education of adolescent moms.

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